

PATTERNS AND QUALITIES OF LEADERSHIP AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

BABETTE B. PASIA¹

DELON A. CHING²

babette.pasia@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-8790-4963¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

Paaralang Elementarya ng Janaojanao, San Juan, Batangas, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

A leader is always a leader no matter what happens, teachers completely perform their job in their different techniques but sometimes it was affected by the way a leader leads the school. This study focused on the patterns and qualities of leadership as predictors of teacher's performance in public elementary schools particularly in San Juan West District, Division of Batangas. This study is a descriptive-correlational kind of research. 106 teacher-respondents were teaching in San Juan West District, Division of Batangas, conducted last March. The study uses a survey questionnaire through the use of google form for easier distribution and collection of data. Based on the result there is a correlation between patterns of leadership and the teacher's performance as well as the correlation between leadership qualities and teacher's performance that is highly manifested. Based on the findings, the communication skills of the leadership qualities of the school heads contributed significantly to the professionalism of teachers-respondents. The researcher recommends that the school heads as leaders have to be aware of the teacher's performance. Patterns and qualities of leadership from the school head may help teachers in performing their job, showing little concern for the teachers make them motivated. Great communication skills with the teachers may provide an accurate decision for attaining the goals in education. Teachers and school heads are builders of a great leader.

Keywords: Patterns of Leadership, Leadership Qualities, Professionalism, Instructional Competence